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Water Quality Analysis Device using Turbidimetry

Optoeletrónica

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Abstract

This study details the creation of a portable water quality analysis device using the physical principle of turbidimetry. Stemming from the LEARN - Winter 2023 program, our project aims to address water contamination concerns in underserved regions. It was made a business model for the assemble of a prototype and the distribution to less developed areas with possible no clean water. This work also presents a brief state-of-art with studies that show the importance of turbidity in the water and its relation to known diseases and different systems that use turbidimetry to analyse water quality. The prototype for the device was successfully built in the class laboratory. Despite some limitations, such as a small sample size and limited contaminants tested, the preliminary results suggest the device's effectiveness. The contaminants used for the tests were bromothymol blue, methyl orange, beer and vinegar and the device measured the turbidity change with this contaminants as we expected. This work highlights turbidimetry as an efficient method for contamination detection, indicating its potential utility in assessing water quality and its importance in the health of the world population. While the study marks a significant step in the device development, further research is needed for broader applicability.

1 Introduction

There is a lot of water in the planet, but a lot of that water is contaminated [1]. In response to this, in the present work we expose a portable device capable of conducting water quality analysis within seconds, thus allowing for fast discrimination between clean and contaminated water.

There are many less developed areas who lack clean water for human consumption, so it is very important to offer an affordable and effective solution for detecting hazardous compounds in water, enabling to the people to avoid consuming water that is contaminated. For example, near abandoned mines and mine waste sites, the surface and underground water contamination represent a significant risk. Contamination, particularly by heavy metals such as Arsenic (As), Cadmium (Cd), Lead (Pb), and Mercury (Hg), which are known for their low solubility in water, presents a significant environmental concern due to their toxicity, non-degradability, persistence, and ability to accumulate in living organisms. Even small quantities of these substances can imply danger to human health, for instance, as little as $1.0\mu\text{g/L}$ of mercury (Hg) can be very toxic for humans [2]. This contamination is not only dangerous for humans, it is dangerous also for rivers and their ecosystems, impacting aquifer geometry, and the quantity and quality of water available for irrigation and consumption purposes [3].

Additionally, monitoring the water quality in mountain lakes is crucial because they are sensitive to climatic changes, anthropogenic pressures, and bacterial presence (e.g. fecal pollution), which can alter the water's pH, exacerbated by uncontrolled tourism [2]. Considering all these consequences, active monitoring of water quality becomes crucial, as it has socio-economic repercussions on society as a whole. It is in the interest of governments worldwide to engage in such monitoring, as it enables the prediction of near-future scenarios and aids in strategic planning for potential interventions [4].

A valuable method for measuring water quality is turbidimetry, which measures the turbidity (cloudiness) of a sample of water by evaluating the transmitted light intensity through it. This technique takes into account how particles in a fixed volume of water absorb and scatter light. It can be implemented using two types of devices (Figure 1): absorptimeters, that measures the light attenuation passing through the sample, and nephelometers, detecting the light scattered at an angle of 90° from the incident beam, that is the most sensitive angle for this type of detection, as endorsed by the EPA (Environmental Protection Agency) [5].

High transmitted light intensity indicates low turbidity, implying that less amount of light is being absorbed and dispersed away from its original path. Accurate measurement of scattered light is crucial to detect particles like silt, clay, algae, organic matter, and microorganisms. For both, transmitted and scattering measurements, choosing the correct light wavelength is very important. To achieve this, the size of the expected particles must be taken into account, as there is a high dependency between the scattering cross section for a certain wavelength in function of the particle size, as illustrated in Figure 1 [5].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the two possible turbidimeters used to measure turbidity. In this report, an absorptimeter was used. However, this image, adapted from Omar et al. (2019) [5], describes the backscattered and nephelometric measurements, illustrating scattered light at an angle θ of 90° and $< 90^\circ$.

The measurement of transmitted light intensity typically employs photodetectors and is expressed as a derivative of the Beer-Lambert's law:

$$I = I_0 e^{-(\alpha a + \alpha b)xc}, \quad (1)$$

here, I represents transmitted light intensity, I_0 denotes incident light intensity, x signifies the medium's length or distance that light travels, c stands for the solution's concentration, αa indicates the absorption coefficient, and αb refers to the scattering coefficient. The total absorption and scattering coefficients are equal to the sum of all particles' absorption and scattering coefficients when a solution contains particles with varying absorbing and scattering coefficients [5]. Figure 2 illustrates the cross-section of Mie and Rayleigh scattering, with Mie occurring when particles are similar in size to the light's wavelength and Rayleigh when particles are significantly smaller than the light's wavelength, representing the limit of Mie scattering [6].

Figure 2: Graphical representation of the scattering light cross-section for Rayleigh and Mie scattering across the wavelength spectrum of visible white light. Particle sizes are 0.0285 μm and 0.2615 μm , respectively. Adapted from Omar et al. (2019) [5].

Moreover, it is essential to recognize that different device designs may produce different values. The turbidity values mentioned in this report are specific to the prototype described herein, calibrated using consistent tap water and following the experimental procedure outlined in section 4.1.

The utilization of this method sparked the initiation of the first phase of the Start For Future program, which involved the creation of a group called "BBA"

2 Problem and proposal

The first step was to identify the problem, which as mentioned in the introduction, involves distinguishing between contaminated water and clean water. Once the problem was identified, the next step was to start considering a solution. This solution needed to be aligned with the scope of the Optoelectronics subject, therefore it needs to use optical and electronic components to solve the problem. This way, after a brainstorming session, it was decided to solve the problem by measuring the loss of light intensity when it passes through a water sample. In order to know if the proposal was reliable, a research was made, detailed in the section 3. During this phase, the technique was identified as turbidimetry, and it was found that it is actually used for the same purpose that is being proposed for, but mainly in investigation centers and hospitals, through very expensive devices.

Therefore, the project's viability was confirmed from both a technical and a commercial perspective, because other authors have used the same technique for similar purposes, and there was no mention of any **cheap** and self-contained device designed for home testing.

3 State of the art

In order to know if the idea is reliable, a research was made in the main scientific journal databases. This research aimed to establish a clear correlation between turbidity and water quality. Accordingly, it will be presented some studies that show the relation between this two concepts.

In a 2020 study [7], it was presented a procedure for assessing the risk of loosing microbiological safety in water quality taking into account the size of the population threatened with waterborne diseases. Turbidity limit values were used as a parameter related to the loss of microbiological water safety. The method consisted in the determination of the probability of threat in waterborne diseases in function of different turbidity levels. This provided a tool for decision-making regarding microbiological testing and notification of crisis management services based on the risk level. The figure 3 shows the reported number of cases of waterborne disease in the USA in 2014.

Figure 3: Waterborne disease outbreaks percentage associated with drinking water in: a) 1006 cases of illness; b) 42 reported outbreaks.

Many studies propose relations between water turbidity levels and diseases [8, 9, 10, 11, 12]. For example, Roberta Muoio et al. [8], showed an association between this parameter and gastroenteritis diseases. In the study, the data were collected from water treatment plants and from several epidemiological studies correlating the incidence of gastrointestinal diseases with turbidity. The conclusions of the authors were that the smaller percentages of turbidity in the water corresponded to the less average daily per-capita risk in outbreaks of waterborne diseases. Additionally, De Ross et al. (2017) [9], after an extensive review of studies about the correlation between gastrointestinal illness and turbidity levels, reached the same conclusion, pointed out that there is a positive association between drinking-water turbidity and gastrointestinal illness incidence.

Eric Foto et al. [13] studied the turbidity and bacterial contamination in natural water sources in Africa. Their objectives were based in the significant reduction in the water turbidity to eliminate nearly all pathogenic microorganisms. The methods consisted in filters that reduce the organic matter to its non-biodegradable fraction, allowing this technique to be of interest for small communities less developed in water quality. Figure 4 presents some of the results of this study.

Figure 4: a) Comparison of turbidity readings in the supply raw water (RW) and receiver filtered water tanks (FW); b) Turbidity change as a function of filtered water volume.

There are other studies [14] that proposes a low-cost turbidity system based on a detector that measures the cloudiness in water, using a microprocessor Intel Galileo 2 and a server for a web-based monitoring system. The system triggers a filtration process that cleans the water when the turbidity level reaches a threshold value. The results obtained demonstrate that the system successfully measured turbidity in different conditions, including total darkness and ambient light and in different scenarios, submerged in still and flowing water. So this system works in real time monitoring the water providing a practical solution for assessing and maintaining water quality.

In another paper [15] an optical tomography system using the ICA method (Independent Component Analysis) was tested in pure and contaminated water. The results obtained in the study showed that the concentration profiles in pure or contaminated water were different and this method showed that the concentration profiles were related to the turbidity level allowing for this level to be estimated. The contaminated testes was algae, that is very common in contaminated waters. This investigators concluded that the experiments can effectively differentiate between pure water and contaminated water providing valuable information for various applications in environmental monitoring and water treatment.

About the correlation with the presence of heavy metals, there are studies that shows that the presence of heavy metals is highly correlated with a change in the levels of turbidity [16]. Also, it was found that the turbidimetry technique can effectively predict the bacterial growth on a sample [17]. About possible competitors, it was found that there are some portable turbidimeters in the market, but usually they are very expensive. For instance, in the article of Marina et al. (2020) [18], the authors use the device Eutech TN-100 (Figure ??), that is available for 940 EUR in the webpage of the manufacturer.

Figure 5: Eutech TN-100 portable turbidimeter. Image from the webpage of the manufacturer.

4 Methodology

4.1 Electronic Prototype

A first prototype of all the electronics for the proposed device was developed, as depicted in Figure 6. This initial version utilizes an Arduino Nano and incorporates only a laser (light source) and a photodiode (detector). The arduino code used is simple because the system only needs to measure the amount of light detected by the photodiode and show it by the serial monitor.

The operation of the circuit is as follows:

- The diode laser is directly connected to the 5V and GND pins of the Arduino Board.
- The photodiode is connected directly to the 5V and through a potentiometer to the GND and A0 pins of the Arduino Board. This way, by using the potentiometer the sensibility of the photodiode can be changed.
- When the laser passes through the water sample, the loss of the intensity will be measured by the photodiode.

Figure 6: Electronic circuit of the prototype. Made with the Fritzing software.

4.2 Mechanical Prototype

In order to safeguard all the electronics and provide support for the components during the initial experiments, a prototype for a 3D mechanical enclosure was devised. This prototype encompassed four crucial parts: laser support, photodiode support, electronics enclosure and a space for the water. Despite the numerous CAD (Computer-Aided Design) modeling software options available, such as SolidWorks, the decision was made to utilize Tinkercad, a simpler online alternative. This choice was rooted in the understanding that it was solely for designing the initial prototype and not the final product. To measure the dimensions of all the electronic prototype components, a caliper was used, allowing for measurements with a resolution of 0.1 mm.

The initial version of the prototype is depicted in Figures 7a and 7b. While this version met all the requirements, it exceeded the size limit for printing on the available 3D printer in the Physics Department. Consequently, a simplified and smaller version was developed, showcased in Figures 7c and 7d. This iteration retained only the essential components required to conduct the initial experiments in a stable manner.

Figure 7: First version of the 3D prototype (a, b), along with the final version (c, d), which has a smaller size and had been reduced to the minimum necessary. In all the figures, from left to right, it can be seen: the enclosure for the Arduino Nano (1), the photodiode support (2), the space to put the water sample (3), and the laser support (4).

4.3 Experiments

After finishing the electronic and mechanical parts of the initial prototype, four tests were performed to evaluate the performance of the proposed device. In each experiment, a small container was filled with tap water, then placed in the designed place for the water sample, and the potentiometer was calibrated until a value of 400 was reached on the photodiode. Subsequently, various quantities of drops of different compounds were added with the help of a dropper, and after waiting for the photodiode to provide a stable reading, the value was recorded. The details about the compounds used are shown in the table 1. As it can be seen, for transparent compounds more drops were used, otherwise, the change in light intensity was too low to be distinguished from the background noise.

Compound	Drops Quantity	Observed color
Bromothymol blue	0, 1, 2, 3, 4	Deep blue, semi transparent.
Methyl orange	0, 1, 2, 3, 4	Bright orange, semi transparent.
Beer	0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100, 150, 200	Light yellow, highly transparent.
Vinegar	0, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500, 600	Almost totally transparent.

Table 1: Compounds used in the experimental phase.

5 Results

5.1 Electronic prototype

The electronic prototype was implemented using the resources available in the Optoelectronics Laboratory. A picture of this implementation is provided in Figure 8. To ensure that all connections were properly made, the detector was tested by directly illuminating it with the laser, as well as with a flashlight, and then completely covering it. It was verified that the output provided by the serial terminal corresponded with the expected results for all cases.

Figure 8: Picture of the implemented electronic circuit.

5.2 Mechanical prototype

The mechanical prototype was printed using the 3D printer available in the Physics Department. The result is shown in Figure 9. Some difficulties were encountered with the laser's radius, which was too tight, but this was resolved by using a sandpaper. For future prototypes, the printer's error at such small scales should be taken into account.

Figure 9: Pictures of the 3D prototype with the laser and photodiode mounted and working.

5.3 Experiments

The obtained results for the tests performed are presented in Figure 10. It can be seen that for each tested compound a loss of the final intensity of the light passing through the initially clean water was detected. It is highly remarkable that for less transparent compounds, such as bromothymol blue and methyl orange, the change in the signal was very fast, reaching values near to 200 and 300 after only 4 drops, respectively. On the other hand, for the vinegar, that is almost totally transparent, it was difficult to detect some change, and it was noted that the value converges to approximately 385. Finally, for a highly transparent compound (but not totally), such as beer, the value decrease slowly but in a better way that for vinegar. Thus, a clear dependency with the transparency of the contamination agent was found. In the case of the beer, the evolution of the color of the water sample in function of the quantity of drops can be observed in Figure 11.

Figure 10: Results of the tests. A clear dependency between the final intensity of the beam and the amount of drops is seen.

Figure 11: Evolution of the transparency of the water sample with the addition of beer drops. Initially completely transparent (a), then at 50 drops (b) and for 100 drops (c) with a sample of beer on the side.

6 Start for Future

The following section of our report consists in a description of the participation process in the Phase 1 LEARN - Winter 2023 project of the Start for Future program. This project allowed the interaction with students from different courses, universities, and countries, as well as discussions on various topics (sustainability, entrepreneurship, startups, how to advance an idea, etc.) with experts in the field.

6.1 Online Sessions

There were five online Zoom sessions in which we participated, discussing and developing our idea with other SFF members. Following, it will be explained what we specifically did in each of those sessions and how we progressed in evolving our idea.

- **Session 1 – Kick-off:** During the initial session, the SFF LEARN program was introduced by the managers, who explained the platform tools and provided details about the project. We also met SFF domain experts who offered valuable insights into their areas of interest.
- **Session 2 – Project Team Peer Review :** In this session, the LEARN managers divided us into breakout rooms with three teams to collaborate and assist each other in developing our ideas. Our breakout room included a ‘Health’ expert who discussed our ideas and aided us in refining them. This breakout room format continued in the subsequent sessions, allowing discussions with these two groups and the expert.
- **Session 3 – Sparring with an Industry Expert:** During the third session, we presented our first pitch deck via PowerPoint, explaining our idea, the main problem we aimed to solve, and the prototype we intended to build in the laboratory. Although we received positive feedback, we were advised to conduct further research and incorporate the selected customer group(s) and market competition into our idea.

- **Session 4 – Business Model Review:** In this session, we presented a second version of our pitch deck and a business model. The expert assisted us in refining our final presentation and pitching skills, providing valuable advice. This marked our final discussion with the expert and the other teams before the ultimate presentation.
- **Session 5 – Final Presentations:** Teams were divided into breakout rooms for each idea area (Health, Manufacturing, Food, Mobility, etc.), where we presented our final three-minute pitch to the jury members. We received positive professional feedback on our performance and idea, engaging in a rewarding discussion with professionals who understood and appreciated our final pitch.

Next, we will provide a brief explanation of the business model developed for our idea. Figure 12 presents the business model with all the sections of our project that were presented to the jury.

6.2 Business Model

The business model aims to present everything relevant to our idea based on the requirements of the SFF program. We present the problem, the solution and the prototype that we won't get in much detail here because it is explained in other sections of this report. Now for the next parts of the business model, it will be explained a bit better because this is the SFF part that was requested and we will not talk about it in the rest of the report.

The poster is titled "IS OUR WATER CLEAN OR CONTAMINATED?" and is divided into several sections:

- THE PROBLEM:** A lot of the water present in our planet is contaminated.
- OUR SOLUTION:** Build a portable device that can conduct water quality analyses in just few seconds. It notes that there are no direct competitors.
- Turbidimetry:** When light goes through water, the intensity of the beam decreases if the water is contaminated. A diagram shows an initial light beam passing through a sample, resulting in a final light beam of lower intensity.
- TESTS:** We made some successful tests with bromothymol blue and methyl orange solution. We are planning to do more tests at least with sugar, vinegar and beer.
- THE PROTOTYPE:** A photograph of the prototype device, which includes a laser, a sample holder, and a photodetector.
- TARGET:** 1. Adventurers, 2. Mining sites, 3. Less developed areas.
- BUSINESS PLAN:**
 - PHASE 1:** Give to adventurers without costs for them to test it and advertise it spreading the word. Starting that way, a marketing strategy.
 - PHASE 2:** Mass production for global distribution and define the prices for selling the device. Starting that way, the actual profit for the company.
- NEXT STEPS:**
 - Add solar panels to make it self-sustainable;
 - Add a bluetooth module to send the data to a smartphone app;
 - Upgrade the device to measure constantly a desired water supply.

Figure 12: Business Model

Competition: The competition is briefly addressed in the 'Our Solution' part of the business model, merely to state that no other companies are utilizing devices similar to ours. While there are portable turbidimeters available, they are considerably costly and function differently from ours. We conducted research and presented the slide depicted in Figure 13 to the expert. Many water quality testing methods are designed to detect specific contaminants, concentrating on identifying particular viruses or bacteria. However, there is no method exclusively dedicated to determining whether water is clean or contaminated without specifying a particular microorganism. Despite the various uses of turbidimetry in detecting contaminants, as previously discussed in section 1, none employ it in the manner we propose.

Target: For the development of our idea, it was asked "What is the target people?". So we thought that individuals residing in less developed areas with access to water from lakes, rivers and other water-related locations must want to find out if that water is drinkable or not, in different days the water is different too because in those places the content inside the water is always changing.

Testing Method	Components Tested	Limitations/Challenges
WaterSafe Kits	Bacteria, Lead, Pesticides, etc.	Limited to specific contaminants; may not cover viruses and small concentrations of chemical compounds like volatile organic compounds and heavy metals.
Safe Home Kits	Metals, Bacteria, Chemicals, etc.	Limited coverage
TDS Meters	Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	Measures overall dissolved solids but doesn't identify specific contaminants.
PurTest Kits	Coliform Bacteria	Primarily focused on bacterial contamination.
WaterCheck Kits	Coliforms, Pesticides, Nitrates, etc.	Primarily focused on bacterial contamination.
pH Testers	Acidity/Alkalinity (pH)	Limited to assessing water's pH level.
MyDx Analyzer	Various Contaminants (Advanced)	Sophisticated but not portable; may be more suitable for advanced analysis.

Figure 13: Table of competitors

Residents in proximity to mining sites and adventurers who enjoy exploring remote locations are other groups of people who might enjoy this technology.

Business Plan: For the business plan we needed to explain a strategy for the sell of our product (device). The phase one was suggested by the expert in the fourth session: select some adventurers, if they are famous like celebrity adventurers it would be better, to give them for free our device. They would use it in a way that they could test and see its efficiency, then they could advertise saying that it works, spreading the word. That way, they would get free technology that would help them in the trails and explorations and we would get started a marketing strategy for more people to know our product. In a phase two, if many people knew and wanted to buy the device, we would mass product it and distribute maybe partnering with NGOs, government agencies, and humanitarian organizations involved in water supply and sanitation could help in the distribution.

Next Steps: In a possible future where all of this succeeded, we would try to upgrade the device. Adding solar panels to make it self-sustainable would be a great improvement. Adding a Bluetooth module would give the possibility to see in a smartphone the quality of the water. Other possible upgrade could be changing the device or selling a different device that would be constantly in a water supply measuring the quality, that way we would see the changes in the contamination daily or constantly.

The development of business and marketing strategies required extensive hours of work. This comprehensive planning makes our idea a well-organized concept, potentially capable of contributing to global welfare. It's crucial to note that these strategies were devised with the assumption that the device works flawlessly as anticipated. However, the implementation of these strategies will take considerable time before coming into fruition. Our aim in formulating these strategies was to conduct thorough research and understand how to transform an idea into a practical solution that can be seamlessly integrated into society.

7 Conclusion

This work presents the assemble of a device capable of conducting water quality analysis within seconds using the physical principle of turbidimetry. The initial motivation behind this idea was addressing the problem "Is our water clean or contaminated?", as we pretended to achieve a way of being one step ahead in the solution to this problem. The Phase 1 LEARN - Winter 2023 project of the Start for Future program helped us facing this matter with discussions with experts and students of different parts of the planet. We also made a business model for the creation and distribution of this portable devices to less developed areas and other places with no clean water.

However, it is crucial to understand the limitations of the study, which had few number of tests and contaminants. It was used a 3D printer in the support for the electronic instruments that were used and

this underscores innovation and adaptability in the construction of the device, but it can be a limitation because of the possible optimization of the manufacturing process that is not cheap. Preliminary results suggest the effectiveness of the device, but the generalization of these conclusions requires a more comprehensive approach, including more contaminants and a broader range of conditions. Anyway, the research that was made strengthens and supports the argument that measuring the turbidity of a water sample allows us to estimate its quality. Many studies emphasize this point and use turbidimetry in various applications showing that this physical principle can be an efficient way to detect if water is contaminated.

It is concluded that this work serves as a valuable starting point for a portable device capable of conducting water analysis through turbidimetry. With a not overly complex experimental part, the device was capable of assessing the turbidity of the water. The SFF program helped us develop the idea of using this device in a practical application to help the world but didn't do much in the progress for the optoelectronics aspect. In any case we are thankful to have been a part of the SFF community and we are satisfied with the realization of this study.

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